

MEMBERSHIP OF GERMAN LANGUAGE TEXTBOOKS CREATED IN SCHOOLS, LYCEUMS, VOCATIONAL COLLEGES AND UNIVERSITIES.

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Annotation: This article discusses the membership of German language textbooks created by schools, lyceums, vocational colleges and universities, the internationalization of education in international society, the basic rules of German language management, interactive methods in German language lessons. described in detail.

Key words: interactive method, textbook continuity, internationalization, modern thinking, globalization.

Introduction:The world is evolving rapidly and cannot meet its growing needs within each individual state. Life requires a combination of experience, strength and the ability to strive for new horizons. This phenomenon is also observed in modern education. The internationalization of education is the result of the globalization of the entire modern world. A new approach to education requires the integration of social and economic life, the integration of different peoples and cultures. In the end, the world will win in every way.

Literature analysis and methodology:

there is a lot of competition for the right to be a leader in this or that field in the world. Education is also in this competitive environment. In modern society, the internationalization of education is taking place, ensuring international educational cooperation. Educational institutions that attract students from different countries are in a good position.

They allow you to acquire knowledge and skills at the level of demand everywhere. The partnership will significantly increase the chances of winning the competition for the right to lead in education. Integration processes are underway in Europe, the Asia-Pacific region, the BRICS, the SCO and the CIS.

Thus, the internationalization of education is one of the factors of international educational cooperation. Cooperation is more important than the struggle for leadership. However, leaders are the ones who have entered the global education space faster and more successfully.

For example, interactive methods in German lessons often focus on developing students' oral skills. In this case, the establishment of student cooperation in small groups allows even the most ignorant, shallow-speaking students to try to say something with the help of their peers, to make the student understand the "understanding" in front of him. I can, but I can't speak

Results:Experiments show that students who learn German as a foreign language are more likely to make mistakes, especially in the formation of phrases through management syntactic communication and in the practical use of such expressions in their speech. In our opinion, it is impossible to master this language, especially oral and written speaking skills, without mastering the basic rules of management that are specific to the German language. This is because the verb or predicative adjectives that come as a dominant word in the German language require the subordinate clause not only to be in the proper conjunction, but they also often have a specific preposition in the phrase. conditional on his arrival.

Discussion:Special attention is paid to the revision of management methods to increase the efficiency of activities in order to implement the priorities of socio-economic development of the country at the modern stage. Therefore, the primary leader is responsible for creating a healthy environment, regardless of any segment of Uzbek society. To do this, we need to find, nurture, appoint responsible leaders who are loyal, responsible, who care about the interests and peace of the people, their well-being, who care about them, who know the work, who have the ability to think and work modernly. , we will achieve our goals only if we define such tasks as continuous monitoring of their activities as a strategic task of public policy. Because the time itself urges us to make up for lost time on the path of development, to overcome the concerns of our people, to prepare the worthy generations of tomorrow and to feel a deeper sense of responsibility to them.

Conclusion:To ensure the constant interaction of the active student with the inactive student in the process of working in pairs (questions and answers, dialogues, role-playing games), even in the performance of homework By sponsoring them, it is possible to turn active learners into assistant teachers by organizing their regular collaboration.

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